

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.4265863

Stable URL:<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4265863>

ISSN 972-33315

jnanadeepa

Pune Journal of Religious Studies

**Religion, Violence and
New World-Order**

Volume 8 No.1

January 2005

Jnanadeepa:
Pune Journal of Religious Studies

Vol. 8 No. 1 January 2005

Contents

Editorial -----	3
A Creative Approach to Violence:A Biblical Perspective ----- <i>Rekha M. Chennattu RA</i>	5
Poverty and Violence: The Influence of Poverty on Destructive Behaviour - <i>Wilhelm Guggenberger</i>	20
Enmity and Political Identity: Friend-Enemy-Patterns and Religion ----- <i>Wolfgang Palaver</i>	35
Is Divine Omnipotence (Non)-Violent?: Reflections from the Viewpoint of Dramatic Theology - <i>Nikolaus Wandinger</i>	50
Religion in the Emerging World Order ----- <i>Jacob Kavunkal SVD</i>	65
The Creative Role of Religion in the Emergence of a Sustainable World-Order ----- <i>Kuruvilla Pandikattu SJ</i>	88
Towards a Communicative Theology ----- <i>Matthias Scharer and Teresa Peter</i>	108
A Spirituality for Our Times ----- <i>Samuel Rayan SJ</i>	127
The Spirituality of a Diocesan Priest ----- <i>Noel Sheth SJ</i>	145
<i>Book Review</i> -----	166

Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies

Editorial Board

Editor

Kurien Kunnumpuram

Secretary

Kuruvilla Pandikattu

Book Review Editor

Rosario Rocha

Associate Editors

Evelyn Monteiro

Isaac Padinjarekutt

Cyril Desbruslais

Lisbert D'Souza

Paul Parathazham

Editorial Advisory Board

Abraham M.C.

Anthony da Silva

Errol D'Lima

Francis D'Sa

George Karuvellil

Jacob Kavunkal

Jacob Parappally

Job Kozhamthadam

John Karuvellil

Lorenzo Fernando

Mathew Jayanth

Mohan Doss

Noel Sheth

Rekha Chennattu

Rui de Menezes

Scaria K.J.

Subhash Anand

Editorial Assistance

Denis Rodrigues

ISSN 0972-3331

Printed at: Anitha

Printers, Pune

Jnanadeepa (=“Light of Wisdom” pronounced as *Jñānadīpa*) is a biannual interdisciplinary journal of religious studies from an Indian Christian perspective. It is closely associated with Jnana Deepa Vidyapeeth: Pontifical Institute of Philosophy and Religion, Pune 411014, India.

Jnanadeepa is published biannually, in January and July. Views expressed by the writers are not necessarily those of the editors. Manuscripts submitted for publication should be original and cannot be returned (writers' style sheet is available on request); they could be sent (preferably as a Word or RTF file) in a computer diskette or through E-mail as file attachment.

All **correspondence** (requests for subscription, manuscripts, books for review – two copies, please – exchange copies of journals, advertisements, etc.) to:

The Editor, *Jnanadeepa*, Jnana Deepa Vidyapeeth, Pune 411014, India

Tel (office): +91-20-27034968,

Tel (residence): +91-20-27034169,
27034497 Fax: +91-20-27034801

E-mail: <kurien@jesuits.net> <jdv@vsnl.com>

Homepage: <http://www.jdvindia.org>

Publisher: JDV Publications

Subscription Rates

Country	One Year	Three Years
India	Rs 80	Rs. 200
SAARC Countries	Rs. 140	Rs. 400
Surface Mail	\$ 16 (Euro)	\$ 45 (Euro)
Air Mail	\$ 20 (Euro)	\$ 55 (Euro)
Institutions	\$40 (Euro)	\$ 110(Euro)
Life Subscription	Rs. 3000 (Indian)	\$ 350(Euro) (Foreign)

Editorial

In September, 2004, an International Conference was held at Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, Pune, in which professors from the University of Innsbruck as well as from the Vidyapeeth took part. The theme of the Conference was *Religion, Violence, Communication and a New World Order*. In this issue of *Jnanadeepa* we publish some of the papers prepared for and presented at the Conference.

These papers easily fall into three groups. One group of four papers deals with Violence. The first paper examines the relationship between poverty and violence. Poverty can be seen as the result of violence when *structural violence* forces a large number of people into poverty and misery. But poverty can also be the cause of violence when misery and want drive people to violence. A study of the Islamic fundamentalists who became agents of terror has convinced the author that it is not the very poor who engage in terrorism and that there is a spiritual dimension to this struggle. They seek to destroy the modern Western culture which is decadent and to usher in a new world order shaped by religious tradition. The second paper discusses the Friend-Enemy Pattern in politics and the impact of religion on this is stressed. From the beginning of human civilization we notice a curious phenomenon. People believe that in order to overcome civil wars inside a society one needs an outside enemy. In our day religion is thought to be responsible for the increase in violence, hatred and enmity. Some believe that a political theology of violence is the offspring of monotheism. But the author contends that it is wrong to accuse monotheism of being responsible for the development of such a theology. A third paper examines Jesus' interpretation of the *lex talionis* (the law of retaliation) found in Matthew 5: 38–42. Basing herself on the experience of the oppressed and the marginalised, the author seeks to interpret the teaching of Jesus by using the Gandhian concept of non-violence and non-cooperation as a hermeneutical key. The author's conclusion is this: Jesus challenges those who are insulted, oppressed or exploited to make a creative and non-violent response that would be a protest against all oppressive systems and dehumanising practices and would enable the victims to recover their human dignity and to restore justice. And a fourth paper discusses the question: Is Divine Omnipotence violent or non-violent? Employing the method of a "dramatic theology", which supposes a real interaction between the Lord of history and the human

agents of history, the author argues that truly a Christian view of divine omnipotence has to conceive it as non violent and as cooperating with human agency.

A second group of two articles deals with a new world order. The first of these discusses the role of religion in the emerging world order. After a careful examination of the life affirming and life-negating factors in the world today, the author points out how religion along with other agencies can contribute to the establishment of a new world order. All religions can and should collaborate in promoting respect for human dignity and in ushering in an era of justice and peace. The other paper deals with the creative role of religion in the emergence of a sustainable world order. The author believes that violence is to some extent inevitable, But the danger we face today is that ours has become an inherently violent society. He looks upon religion as a mid-wife which assists at the birthing of a new humanity and a new world order. The perennial religious values and mystical insights provide us with the hope that we can overcome violence and create a new world order in freedom, peace and joy.

The third group has only one paper which deals with communicative theology. Part one of this paper seeks to compare communicative theology with theology as cross-cultural encounter, while part two discusses the main elements of communicative theology.

Included in this issue are two papers on spirituality which were originally written for the last issue of Jnanadeepa but which, because of some technical problems, were not published then. The first of these seeks to develop a theology for our times. The author contends that for us Christians, spirituality for today consists in an openness and commitment to the Reign of God which Jesus announced in his ministry, served all his life and embodied in his person. An essential element of this spirituality will be the weaving and cherishing of a vision of world solidarity, recognising the equality, dignity and the rights of all persons, groups and nations, irrespective of geography, race, colour, culture, gender, age or status. The other paper develops the spirituality of the diocesan priest. It describes the main elements of the secular spirituality of the diocesan priest which is a spirituality of involvement in the world. It also points out certain aspects of Indian spirituality that would help diocesan priests in India to be more inculturated.

It is our fond hope that the articles in this issue of Jnanadeepa will be of some help to those engaged in the contemporary quest for a peaceful world free from all violence.

Kurien Kunnumpuram SJ
Editor